

Institutional Operationalisation of the Converging EU Digital Rulebook for Trustworthy AI-in-Health Research

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) research using clinical data is governed by an increasingly convergent European digital rulebook comprising the GDPR, the NIS2 Directive, the AI Act and the European Health Data Space Regulation. These instruments impose cumulative duties concerning data protection, cyber-resilience, algorithmic risk governance and secondary use of health data. This article argues that the central challenge for research-performing institutions is not awareness of these legal regimes, but their operationalisation through roles, procedures, registers, templates and auditable systems. Because AI systems are developed and deployed by institutions rather than governments, trustworthy health AI ultimately depends on institutional capacity. The issue is especially acute for EU Widening countries and candidate states, where comparable research ambitions meet weaker institutional scaffolding and, as third countries, obligations to harmonise national law. Drawing on a benchmarking exchange between institutions in North Macedonia and Slovenia within the Horizon Europe ChatMED project (GA: 101159214), the article develops a six-layer Institutional Accountability Architecture and a minimum institutional baseline for implementing trustworthy AI-in-health research governance.

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1. Introduction

The deployment of AI on medical data triggers an unusually dense web of concurrent legal duties. A single research workflow, for example, processing neurological patient records to develop a clinical natural-language model, simultaneously activates: the GDPR, because it processes special-category clinical data; the NIS2 Directive, because it relies on networks and information systems that must be secured and kept resilient; the AI Act, because the clinical application may constitute a high-risk, standalone AI deployment or software-as-a-medical-device; and the EHDS Regulation, which governs the cross-border secondary use of European health data. Drafted on separate tracks and administered by distinct authorities, these rules intersect acutely when applied to medical AI; as commentators observe, the newest of them overlays rather than displaces the others, so compliance positions must be assessed cumulatively rather than instrument by instrument (Shabani, 2022; Kaminski and Malgieri, 2021).

For research-performing institutions, especially those in EU Widening countries and candidate states, the difficulty is rarely a conceptual misunderstanding of what the rulebook requires. The substantive obligations are legible from the legislative text, the guidance of supervisory authorities, and the experience of consortium partners. The difficulty is operationalisation, meaning converting statutory text into the concrete machinery of an institution. Questions such as who serves as the Data Protection Officer, which template governs a controller–processor relationship, where the AI-system register is held, what the incident-response workflow is, how an auditor’s document set is assembled, and under which agreement health-system data may lawfully be used are only a few of the issues that must be answered at the institutional level. Where this machinery is absent, compliance exists only on paper, and the institution cannot

credibly enter, or coordinate, a competitive, multi-institutional EU health-AI consortium.

This points to a more fundamental observation that motivates the article.
30 AI systems are not built, trained or deployed by governments; they are built by institutions such as universities, research centres, hospitals, and companies. Governments legislate, designate competent authorities, and transpose directives, but the locus at which an AI system actually meets the law is the institution that develops it. This shifts the analytical and policy focus of “AI
35 governance” from the legislative level, where most attention has concentrated, to the institutional level, where compliance is either enacted or quietly fails - and it is at this level that Widening and third-country institutions are least equipped and most exposed.

This study was motivated by the ChatMED project (GA 101159214), a Horizon Europe WIDERA Twinning action designed to strengthen research and institutional capacity for generative AI in medicine in a Widening-country setting.
40 During the implementation of ChatMED, it became clear that capacity-building in AI-in-health research cannot be limited to scientific training, technical infrastructure, or model development. If research outputs are expected to move towards clinical, institutional, or public-sector practice, the host institution must
45 also develop the legal, organisational and technical capability to demonstrate trustworthy governance.

In this context, benchmarking emerged as a natural project activity. A Short-Term Staff Exchange (STSE) at the Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana
50 was used not only for individual training, but also as a structured opportunity to compare institutional procedures, project-management practices, data-protection mechanisms, cybersecurity readiness, AI governance expectations and health-data access arrangements. The present paper grew out of that benchmarking exercise.

55 Although the empirical case is rooted in a Widening-country faculty, the problem addressed by the paper is generally applicable to any institution that develops AI systems. The Widening context makes this need more visible be-

cause national harmonisation, supervisory practice and institutional procedures may still be developing.

60 The contribution of this paper is therefore twofold. Empirically, it presents a case study of how a WIDERA capacity-building project generated an institutional benchmarking process around the GDPR, NIS2, the AI Act and the EHDS. Conceptually, it proposes an Institutional Accountability Architecture - IAA that is transferable beyond the Widening context and applicable to any
65 research-performing institution. The FCSE case is used not as an exceptional local problem, but as an illustrative case of a broader transition: from AI research capacity to AI governance capacity.

This transition also suggests that research institutions should move beyond ad hoc compliance checklists and towards management-system thinking.
70 ISO/IEC 42001:2023, as the international standard for Artificial Intelligence Management Systems, provides a relevant organisational reference point for institutions that design, develop, provide or use AI systems (ISO/IEC 42001, 2023). For research institutions, alignment with ISO/IEC 42001 can help structure policies, responsibilities, risk assessment, lifecycle controls, documentation,
75 monitoring, internal review and continuous improvement. While formal certification may not be immediately necessary or feasible for every university or laboratory, the standard offers a practical vocabulary for converting AI governance from a project-by-project exercise into a repeatable institutional capability. The relevant standards and their institutional roles are summarised in
80 Table 2 (Section 8).

The remainder of the article proceeds as follows. Section 2 sets out the four regimes, and Section 3 positions the article against existing work. Section 4 presents the case context, and Section 5 the approach and materials. Section 6 reports the readiness gaps. Section 7 presents the architecture, Section 8 aligns
85 it with management-system standards, and Section 9 distils it into a minimum institutional baseline. Sections 10 and 11 discuss the implications and conclude.

2. Background

2.1. *GDPR Accountability and Cross-border Asymmetries*

The General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) enforces rigorous accountability protocols. A central example is the Data Protection Impact Assessment under Article 35, which applies to high-risk, large-scale processing of sensitive data. The concept of “sensitive” data is itself contested at the margins. This complicates an institution’s first compliance step, namely classifying what it holds (Quinn and Malgieri, 2021). In multi-institutional medical AI research, clarifying the boundary between data controllers and processors (Articles 4, 26 and 28) is legally paramount. Yet this boundary is frequently unclear. The fit between the GDPR and the realities of digital health governance has also been the subject of sustained critique (Marelli et al., 2020). This friction is aggravated for third countries. Intra-EU institutions benefit from more fluid data sharing under standardised norms. By contrast, third-country institutions must govern cross-border processing through bespoke mutual transfer agreements. These agreements may require prior clearance from national authorities under Articles 44–49, even where those authorities are under-resourced. A directly relevant exemplar of GDPR operationalisation in this setting decomposes the obligations into a documented sequence of questions tied to the data life cycle (Gültekin Várkonyi and Gradišek, 2020). The broader convergence of impact-assessment practice across data protection and AI law has been theorised in the algorithmic impact assessment literature (Kaminski and Malgieri, 2021; Mantelero, 2018).

2.2. *NIS2 Systemic Resilience and Hybrid Threats*

The NIS2 Directive (Directive (EU) 2022/2555) scales up cybersecurity compliance. It mandates formalised risk management, supply chain vulnerability mapping, and stringent breach notification workflows. It also builds on and tightens the original NIS framework, whose interaction with the GDPR has been previously analysed (Markopoulou et al., 2019). In contemporary clinical and

computational research environments, cybersecurity can no longer be treated as an isolated technical parameter. It is a pillar of socio-technical resilience against hybrid threats targeting critical healthcare infrastructure (Jandroković, 2026). Technical workflows must therefore merge NIS2 security baselines with the structural safeguards independently demanded by GDPR Article 32.

2.3. AI Act Algorithmic Governance and the Medical-device Interface

The AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) enforces a risk based classification hierarchy. It distinguishes between prohibited, high risk, limited risk, and minimal risk systems (Veale and Zuiderveen Borgesius, 2021; Edwards, 2022). Many medical AI applications fall within the high risk tier. Institutions therefore face substantial duties on data governance quality, logging, transparency, human oversight, accuracy, and conformity assessment. The Act applies in phases. The prohibitions and the Article 4 **AI literacy** mandate have applied since 2 February 2025. Obligations for general purpose AI models have applied since 2 August 2025. The principal high risk obligations apply from 2 August 2026, subject to deferrals introduced by the 2025–2026 “Digital Omnibus” simplification package. Where an AI system constitutes software as a medical device, institutions must synchronise the AI Act with the Medical Device Regulation (MDR). This is necessary to avoid regulatory gridlock that could delay clinical translation; Section 4 reports the state of the corresponding national instrument in the case country. Each Member State must designate competent supervisory authorities. Institutions must also identify those authorities in practice. For candidate countries, this includes identifying the bodies that would play an analogous role. This is a concrete prerequisite for any institution that must know who will oversee its systems.

2.4. EHDS and Semantic Interoperability

The European Health Data Space Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2025/327) restructures the secondary use of clinical records (EHDS2) for research and innovation. Access is brokered through national Health Data Access Bodies

145 within secure processing environments (Shabani, 2022). The Regulation applies in stages. General application starts from 26 March 2027. The secondary use regime starts from 26 March 2029. Each Member State must designate a Health Data Access Body by March 2027. Preparing for this landscape demands more than legal compliance. It also requires adherence to evolving discoverability and semantic interoperability standards. Relevant examples include Health
150 Level Seven Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (HL7 FHIR), the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM), and the Data Catalogue Vocabulary Application Profile (DCAT-AP) (Hussein et al., 2024, 2025). Member State readiness for these demands is markedly
155 heterogeneous even within the Union (Kessissoglou et al., 2024).

2.5. Convergence

The four instruments intersect rather than run in parallel. A high risk AI Act system that processes health data triggers a GDPR DPIA. It may also trigger a fundamental rights impact assessment. The AI Act’s data governance duties
160 echo GDPR requirements on minimisation and accuracy. The security measures demanded by NIS2 substantially overlap with GDPR Article 32. EHDS secondary use access presupposes a GDPR compliant lawful basis and a defined controller/processor architecture. An institution therefore cannot operationalise one regime in isolation. It needs an architecture in which a single artefact can
165 discharge obligations across several regimes at once. Examples include a Data Management Plan, a register entry, or a data sharing agreement.

3. Related Work

Four strands of existing work touch this problem without occupying the same space. First, *readiness studies* assess preparedness for the EHDS at the level of
170 **countries** or national health systems. Examples include the TEHDAS country mapping exercise across twelve Member States (Kessissoglou et al., 2024). Another example is the comparison of secondary use policy readiness across five

Western Balkan countries, including North Macedonia (ODI, 2023). These studies analyse policy and infrastructure at national scale. They do not examine the operational machinery of an individual research performing institution. Second, *single regime implementation studies* show how one regulation is enacted in one organisation. One example is the implementation of a national clinical data warehouse framework at a university hospital (Riou et al., 2025). This work is GDPR centric and hospital based. It is not multi regime and faculty based. Third, *project level interoperability tooling* supports consortia in meeting standards (Hussein et al., 2025). It does not address institutional roles, retention, audit, or supervisory mapping. Fourth, *organisational AI governance models* describe AI governance as a layered phenomenon (Gasser and Almeida, 2017; Mäntymäki et al., 2022). They complement principle level frameworks such as the EU High Level Expert Group’s guidelines (HLEG, 2019) and the NIST AI Risk Management Framework (NIST, 2023). Yet these models address the AI Act adjacent governance problem alone. They do not integrate it with the GDPR, NIS2, and the EHDS. The present contribution occupies the intersection these strands leave open. It proposes an institution-level, multi-regime, Widening/third country operationalisation model derived through Twinning based benchmarking. Its unit of analysis is a single research performing faculty rather than a country, a hospital, or a project. To the authors’ knowledge, no existing study integrates the GDPR, NIS2, the AI Act, the EHDS, and EU project governance obligations into a single layered institutional architecture for a non-Member State research institution. Existing work also gives limited attention to an important distinction. EU Member States apply EU regulations directly, while candidate countries must first harmonise their national law and institutional procedures with those rules.

4. Case Context

The empirical grounding is situated within ChatMED GA 101159214. This is a Horizon Europe WIDERA Twinning project that develops a capacity boost-

ing program combined with a generative AI application in neurology. The coordinating institution is FCSE, which is part of the Ss. Cyril and Methodius University. FCSE represents the highest concentration of technical AI research capacity in North Macedonia. The national State Audit Office reports that FCSE and the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technologies together account for well over 1,700 undergraduate, 220 master's, and 37 doctoral theses related to AI. Yet the same body found a stark paradox. Advanced engineering capability exists alongside an absence of national frameworks, strategy, and institutional coordination for AI. None of the AI projects co-financed through the national innovation fund since 2012 has been implemented in the public sector (State Audit Office RNM, 2024).

This mismatch is exacerbated by an uneven domestic regulatory landscape. North Macedonia transposed the GDPR through its 2020 Law on Personal Data Protection, which was amended in 2025. However, the supervisory authority, the Agency for Personal Data Protection, operates with constrained capacity relative to peers such as the Slovenian Information Commissioner. The European Commission has also noted that the law was adopted without full consultation of that authority. The domestic Law on Security of Network and Information Systems transposing NIS2 entered into force on 1 January 2026. Its implementing bylaws remain pending. There is no national law aligned with the AI Act. Only sectoral provisions exist. There is also no national law aligned with the EHDS. This produces the doctrinal asymmetry on which the article turns. A Member State may rely on the direct effect of an EU regulation. By contrast, a candidate country must first harmonise its existing legislation. This is a slower path and places greater weight on institutional self organisation in the interim. A concrete and current illustration of this harmonisation in progress concerns medical devices. In April 2026 the Ministry of Health of North Macedonia published a draft Law on Medical Devices on the national Electronic Register of Regulations (ENER) and opened a public consultation, as part of a broader reform amending twelve health-sector laws; the procedure is ongoing. For AI systems that qualify as software as a medical device, this is the national instru-

ment that must eventually be synchronised with the AI Act, as discussed in Section 2. Internally, FCSE’s data protection procedures date from 2014 and
235 were never effectively updated. Until April 2026, there was no functioning DPO arrangement. There is also no settled controller–processor positioning.

The appropriate controller–processor allocation is not fixed. It depends on the configuration of each processing activity. Under the GDPR, the controller is the party that determines the purposes and means of processing (Article 4(7)),
240 so the role follows the data flow rather than the institution, and a single entity can be a controller for one operation and a processor for another. Three configurations recur in the present setting. First, the partner health institution acts as controller for the primary processing of medical data within its clinical activity, since it collects and holds those data as a healthcare provider. Sec-
245 ond, FCSE acts as a separate controller when it independently determines the research purpose, methodology, model, analysis, retention period, and access arrangements for the scientific reuse of the data. Third, FCSE acts as a processor when it operates solely on the documented instructions of the health institution. In practice the configuration shifts with the operational scenario. FCSE may
250 store data that it is not authorised to use, store data that it is also authorised to analyse, or analyse data remotely on the health institution’s own infrastructure, and each of these implies a different allocation of roles, including, in some cases, joint controllership under Article 26. The data-sharing agreements currently in force, which designate FCSE as processor and the health institution
255 as controller, reflect one such configuration. The operational point is that each agreement must be matched to the actual processing it governs rather than to a fixed institutional default.

5. A Cross-border Benchmarking

The study adopts a qualitative, single-case, action-oriented approach in
260 which a STSE in May 2026 serves as the pivot between diagnosis and design.

5.1. Phase 1: Pre-exchange Regulatory Diagnostic.

Phase 1 consisted of a structured desk review with two strands.

- The *national strand* inventoried the relevant Macedonian instruments and their state of operationalisation. These included the 2020/2025 Law on Personal Data Protection and its bylaws, the NIS2 transposition in force
265 from January 2026 with bylaws pending, the sectoral treatment of AI, and the digital health systems relevant to EHDS readiness.
- The *institutional strand* reviewed FCSE’s own procedures. These included the 2014 data protection rules and the draft international projects rule-
270 book. The review mapped each obligation against current practice and identified role gaps, notably the absence of an active DPO arrangement before April 2026 and the continuing need for a designated security officer.

The diagnostic did not only identify gaps. It also identified first steps that could help close them. The DPO certification obtained in April 2026 was treated
275 as a response to the earlier absence of an active DPO arrangement. Possible ISO/IEC 27001 certification for information security and ISO/IEC 27701 certification for privacy information management were treated as potential responses to the security and privacy management gaps. These measures matter institutionally because they convert individual readiness into documented organisational
280 capacity. They may also strengthen future EU proposal evaluations.

5.2. Phase 2: Member State Benchmarking.

Phase 2 consisted of a benchmarking field study at JSI in Ljubljana. The study gathered material through three sources.

- Structured questions and answers with JSI’s international office, project management staff, and legal secretariat.
285
- Review of JSI’s procedures for managing international projects, its GDPR summary, and its AI Act briefing materials.

- Observation of JSI’s project management and finance system.

The exchange focused on five themes.

- 290
- Data protection and retention.
 - Cybersecurity formalisation.
 - AI Act supervisory mapping.
 - EHDS readiness.
 - Project management and audit practice.

295 These themes were selected because each could feed directly into the design step.

5.3. Phase 3: Operational Translation.

Phase 3 translated the diagnostic findings and benchmark insights into faculty level mechanisms. These mechanisms included the following elements.

- 300
- Institutional roles.
 - Written procedures.
 - Document templates.
 - Registers.
 - Supporting systems.

305 Figure 1 summarises the methodological pathway through which ChatMED’s capacity-building objective generated a structured benchmarking exercise and, ultimately, an institutional accountability architecture which details are presented in Section 7.

310 The approach has the characteristic limits of a single, formative partner pair design. Its purpose is to offer a transferable template and an honest gap diagnosis. It does not evaluate long run effectiveness, which remains for future

Figure 1: Three-phased methodological pathway from project motivation to institutional architecture.

work. Several findings include gaps observed at the benchmark partner itself. Reporting these gaps makes clear that JSI is used as a benchmark partner for comparison and learning, not as a fully completed compliance model.

315 6. Results

A salient cross cutting finding is that compliance under the converging rule-book is an unstable, moving target across the entire Union. It is not a static baseline that developing countries simply lag behind. Even the Member State benchmark partner had limited formalised internal documentation because those
 320 frameworks are still new. Table 1 summarises the per domain analysis. The discussion that follows expands the doctrinally salient points.

Table 1: Institutional readiness matrix for operationalising the EU digital rulebook in AI-in-health research. Codes score *institutional* artefacts, not national transposition.

Domain	Legal / governance trigger	FCSE	JSI	Required institutional artefact
GDPR / data protection	Special-category health data; DPIA, accountability, controller–processor allocation, transfers, retention.	P	E	Updated data-protection procedure; DPO mandate; DPIA template aligned with the DMP; controller–processor and data-sharing agreements; reconciled retention and transfer workflow.
NIS2 / cybersecurity	Cyber risk management, incident handling, access control, logging, continuity, management accountability; also GDPR Art. 32.	P	P	Faculty cybersecurity policy; incident-response workflow; asset inventory; access-control and logging practice; backups; ISO/IEC 27001 pathway.
AI Act / AI governance	Risk classification, technical documentation, record-keeping, human oversight, transparency, robustness, AI literacy.	Ant.	P	AI-system register; risk-classification checklist; human-oversight procedure; transparency and logging practice; AI-literacy records; ISO/IEC 42001-aligned controls.
EHDS / health-data access	Lawful access to electronic health data, secondary use, purpose limitation, secure processing, interoperability.	Ant.	Ant.	Health-data access workflow; MoH/data-holder cooperation template; purpose-of-use form; anonymisation/synthetic-data procedure; HL7 FHIR/OMOP/DCAT-AP orientation.
Project & audit governance	Grant implementation, financial traceability, audit evidence, role allocation, procurement, closeout.	E	E	Central project registry; role-based access; timesheets; procurement and travel evidence; audit document pack; closeout workflow.

Continued on next page

Domain	Legal / governance trigger	FCSE	JSI	Required institutional artefact
Integrated management system <i>(cross-cutting)</i>	Move from ad hoc compliance to repeatable organisational AI governance.	A	A	ISO/IEC 42001-aligned AI management system linking policy, roles, lifecycle controls, risk management, monitoring, review and improvement. ISO/IEC 27001 and 27701 support security and privacy.

Legend: E = established; P = partial / in transition; A = absent; Ant. = anticipatory alignment (no applicable national law yet); N/A = not applicable. Entries reflect a formative, single-case assessment, not a validated maturity score.

325 The JSI management-system cell records the absence of ISO/IEC 27001, 27701 and 42001 certification; JSI does operate an ISO 9001:2015 quality-management system and nuclear quality assurance, as discussed in Section 8.

GDPR. The GDPR findings are reported at the level of institutional readiness rather than as a compliance audit. The central issue is the need to align project documentation, data-protection roles, retention practice, and data-sharing workflows into one repeatable process. The benchmark showed that 330 mature institutions rely on consistent templates and clear responsibilities rather than ad hoc project-by-project decisions.

NIS2. The cybersecurity finding is framed as an organisational maturity issue. 335 The relevant gap is not a single technical weakness. It is the need to translate security practice into documented institutional procedure. This includes policy, incident handling, asset awareness, access control, logging, backups, and management-system thinking.

AI Act. The AI Act finding concerns preparedness for risk-based governance. 340 Strong AI research capacity must be matched by registers, risk-classification routines, oversight procedures, transparency practices, and AI-literacy training. Benchmarking was useful because it showed how supervisory mapping can be prepared before national implementation is fully settled.

EHDS. The EHDS finding is deliberately stated at a general level because

345 the framework is new and institutional practice is still forming. The main readiness issue is the need to prepare lawful access routes, privacy-preserving data workflows, and interoperability orientation. This should be done without presenting any partner institution as already fully adapted to the EHDS.

Project governance. The project-governance finding concerns repeatability and audit readiness. The benchmark highlighted the value of centralised project 350 information, clear internal roles, financial traceability, and prepared audit documentation. These elements are relevant because they turn compliance from an individual effort into an institutional capability.

7. The Institutional Accountability Architecture

355 We propose a six-layered Institutional Accountability Architecture (IAA) as an alternative to fragmented administrative measures for each regulation. The architecture treats the GDPR, NIS2, the AI Act and the EHDS as a connected governance environment rather than as separate compliance silos. Its organising principle is artefact reuse. This means that institutions should design documents, registers, procedures and technical controls so that each artefact supports 360 several legal duties at the same time. For example, a Data Management Plan entry can support both GDPR accountability and EHDS secondary-use governance. A security control can support both NIS2 resilience obligations and GDPR Article 32. An AI-system registry can support AI governance, internal 365 oversight and audit preparation. The six layers are set out below. Section 8 then explains how the architecture can be aligned with established management-system standards.

7.1. Layer 1: Regulatory Governance

The first layer establishes who is responsible for regulatory governance inside 370 the institution. It assigns clear ownership to a certified Data Protection Officer, an Information Security Officer, an AI-Governance Lead, an ethics contact and the project coordinator. Each role should have a defined mandate, a documented reporting line and a clear connection to project-level decision making.

This prevents compliance tasks from being treated as informal or occasional duties. The institution should also maintain an up-to-date map of the competent external authorities that may become relevant for data protection, cybersecurity, AI governance, health-data access and research ethics. This authority map is especially important in settings where national implementation is still developing or where cross-border projects must interact with several supervisory bodies (Section 6).

7.2. Layer 2: Data Governance

The second layer connects the Data Management Plan and the Data Protection Impact Assessment into one coordinated data-governance process. The institution should use a single data-lifecycle map to describe what data are collected, why they are needed, who may access them, where they are stored, how long they are retained and when they are deleted or anonymised. This map can then serve both funder expectations for responsible research-data management and GDPR accountability requirements, including purpose limitation, data minimisation and storage limitation. A reconciled retention rule is important because research plans, ethics approvals and data-protection documentation often describe retention differently if they are prepared in isolation. The same layer also standardises controller–processor agreements and data-sharing agreements, so that multi-institutional clinical data processing is governed by clear and reusable contractual templates rather than by ad hoc negotiations for every project.

7.3. Layer 3: Cybersecurity

The third layer establishes a single cybersecurity baseline for research projects that use clinical or other sensitive data. This baseline should be mapped both to the national transposition of NIS2 and to GDPR Article 32, because the same technical and organisational controls often support both cyber-resilience and personal-data security. At minimum, the institution should maintain asset

logs, role-based access controls, encrypted-storage rules and a concrete incident-reporting workflow. These measures make it easier to identify affected systems, restrict access to authorised users, protect stored data and respond consistently
405 when a security event occurs. ISO/IEC 27001 can serve as a longer-term reference point for turning these controls into a formal information-security management system.

7.4. *Layer 4: Algorithmic Governance*

The fourth layer governs the AI system itself across the research lifecycle. Every research application should first pass through an internal AI risk-
410 classification checklist to determine whether the proposed system falls within the scope of the AI Act and whether it may qualify as high risk. Where the system may also operate as software-as-a-medical-device, this classification should be coordinated with the MDR assessment rather than handled separately. Models
415 that meet the institutional threshold for governance should then be recorded in an AI-system registry. The registry should document data lineage, model purpose, logging practices, evaluation results and human-oversight mechanisms, so that the institution can explain how the system was developed and controlled. Mandatory AI-literacy seminars should complement the registry by en-
420 suring that researchers understand the legal and organisational responsibilities attached to AI development, including the Article 4 AI-literacy requirement. This layered approach is consistent with organisational models of AI governance that connect institutional responsibility to project-level controls (Gasser and Almeida, 2017; Mäntymäki et al., 2022).

425 7.5. *Layer 5: Health Data Space Interoperability*

The fifth layer prepares the institution for lawful secondary use of health data under the emerging EHDS framework. The institution should establish access routes through Memoranda of Understanding with national health authorities and clinical data providers, so that research use is based on documented permis-
430 sions rather than informal data-sharing arrangements. It should also prioritise

automated anonymisation and synthetic-data pipelines where these methods can reduce exposure to identifiable clinical data without undermining research value. Interoperability should be treated as a governance requirement rather than only as a technical preference. Clinical data structures should therefore be aligned
435 with HL7 FHIR and the OMOP Common Data Model, while DCAT-AP specification can support discoverability of datasets and metadata. These steps help the institution prepare for future EHDS participation by making health-data access more lawful, safer and easier to integrate across systems.

7.6. *Layer 6: Project Management & Audit Readiness*

440 The sixth layer turns project administration into an auditable institutional process. The institution should use a centralised registry to monitor international-project execution, including budgets, accounting sub-accounts, deliverables, reporting deadlines and responsible staff. This registry should be linked to pre-assembled audit document packs that contain employment records, time allocations,
445 transactions, procurement files, financial justifications and relevant approvals. Keeping these materials together reduces dependence on individual memory and makes evidence available before an audit request arrives.

Figure 2 summarises the six-layer Institutional Accountability Architecture and its artefact-reuse logic across the converging EU digital rulebook.

450 **8. ISO Alignment**

The six layers describe *what* an institution must hold and *who* owns it. To convert these elements from a project-by-project effort into a repeatable institutional capability, the architecture can be mapped onto established international management-system standards, which supply a common vocabulary for policies,
455 responsibilities, risk assessment, lifecycle controls, documentation, monitoring, internal review and continuous improvement. Table 2 sets out the standards most relevant to the architecture and their institutional roles. Formal certification is not a precondition for any individual project, and may be neither

Figure 2: Six-layer Institutional Accountability Architecture for operationalising trustworthy AI-in-health research governance.

immediately feasible nor proportionate for every institution. The value lies in
 460 adopting the structure these standards encode. ISO/IEC 42001:2023 is of partic-
 ular interest because it is the first management-system standard specific to AI,
 and it dovetails with the AI-governance layer (Layer 4) much as ISO/IEC 27001
 underpins the cybersecurity layer (Layer 3) and ISO/IEC 27701 reinforces the
 data-governance layer (Layer 2) (ISO/IEC 42001, 2023; ISO/IEC 27001, 2022;
 465 ISO/IEC 27701, 2025; ISO/IEC 23894, 2023).

In the present case, FCSE holds none of these certifications and treats the
 standards as design references rather than immediate certification targets. The
 benchmarking exchange also sought to establish which, if any, of these manage-
 ment systems the Member-State partner maintains, since that materially shapes
 470 how realistic certification is as a medium-term goal for a Widening institution.

JSI, our reference institution, operates a formal quality-assurance programme,
 although its certified standardisation is not centred on the digital rulebook.
 The programme is built on ISO 9001:2015 and, for nuclear technology, on the

Table 2: ISO standards and their institutional roles within the IAA.

Standard	Institutional role
ISO/IEC 27001	Information Security Management System. It supports NIS2-aligned cybersecurity and GDPR Article 32 security safeguards (Layer 3).
ISO/IEC 27701	Privacy Information Management System. It supports GDPR accountability, controller–processor discipline and privacy governance (Layer 2).
ISO/IEC 42001	AI Management System. It supports AI governance, risk management, impact assessment, lifecycle control, monitoring and continuous improvement (Layer 4).
ISO/IEC 23894	AI risk-management guidance. It is a useful companion to ISO/IEC 42001 for AI risk assessment (Layer 4).

United States nuclear quality-assurance requirements of 10 CFR 50 Appendix B.

475 It includes documented administrative and technical procedures for research projects, and it also provides a basis for laboratory accreditation under ISO/IEC 17025:2017 (JSI, 2019). For EURATOM projects it applies ISO 9001:2015, while for other international projects it follows the standards set by the project coordinator. JSI reported no certification against ISO/IEC 27001, 27701 or 42001.
 480 This is itself an informative benchmarking result. Even a mature Member-State institute anchors its certified management systems in quality assurance and nuclear safety rather than in the information-security, privacy and AI-governance standards that the converging digital rulebook now makes salient.

For a Widening institution such as FCSE the practical implication is twofold.

485 The organisational discipline of a management-system culture is transferable and worth emulating, but the digital-rulebook standards that underpin Layers 2 to 4 will in most cases have to be built rather than inherited from partners. This reinforces the opportunity, noted in Section 10, to design clean compliance layers from the outset.

490 **9. A Minimum Institutional Baseline**

Table 1 diagnoses where an institution stands, and Table 2 situates the architecture within management-system standards. Neither table states the concrete actions that an institution must take first. Table 3 distils the IAA into a minimum institutional baseline. It lists the artefacts and roles that a research-performing institution should put in place before it conducts AI-in-health research intended for real-world deployment. Each task is mapped to the regulation or regulations that it primarily serves and to the architectural layer that it instantiates. Many tasks discharge obligations under more than one regime, which reflects the artefact-reuse principle of the architecture. The baseline is deliberately minimal and generic. It offers a transferable starting point rather than legal advice or a certification standard. The precise scope and the mandatory status of each item depend on the risk class of the specific system and on the applicable national and institutional rules.

Table 3: Minimum institutional baseline for trustworthy AI-in-health research, derived from the IAA.

Task / artefact	Affected regulation(s)	Layer
<i>Layer 1. Regulatory governance</i>		
Appoint a DPO with a written mandate and reporting line	GDPR (Art. 37 to 39)	L1
Designate an Information Security Officer	NIS2, GDPR Art. 32	L1
Designate an AI-Governance Lead	AI Act	L1
Maintain a competent-authority map	GDPR, NIS2, AI Act, EHDS	L1
<i>Layer 2. Data governance</i>		
Replace the legacy data-protection procedure with a current one	GDPR	L2
Adopt a DPIA template and require it for high-risk processing	GDPR Art. 35, AI Act	L2, L4
Maintain a single data-lifecycle map linking the DMP and DPIA	GDPR, EHDS	L2, L5

Continued on next page

Task / artefact	Affected regulation(s)	Layer
Set one reconciled data-retention and deletion rule	GDPR Art. 5(1)(e)	L2
Adopt controller, processor and data-sharing agreement templates	GDPR Art. 26, 28	L2
Define a third-country transfer workflow where relevant	GDPR Art. 44 to 49	L2
<i>Layer 3. Cybersecurity</i>		
Adopt a cybersecurity policy mapped to NIS2 and GDPR Art. 32	NIS2, GDPR Art. 32	L3
Maintain an asset inventory	NIS2	L3
Enforce role-based access control	NIS2, GDPR Art. 32	L3
Operate a logging and audit-trail system	NIS2, AI Act, GDPR	L3, L4
Maintain backup and business-continuity procedures	NIS2	L3
Establish an incident-response and breach-notification workflow	NIS2, GDPR Art. 33 to 34	L3
<i>Layer 4. Algorithmic governance</i>		
Create and maintain an internal AI-system register	AI Act	L4
Apply an AI risk-classification checklist, coordinated with the MDR where the system is software as a medical device	AI Act, MDR	L4
Define a human-oversight procedure for deployed systems	AI Act	L4
Keep technical documentation and transparency records per system	AI Act	L4
Run AI-literacy training and keep attendance records	AI Act Art. 4	L4
<i>Layer 5. Health-data-space interoperability</i>		
Conclude cooperation agreements for lawful health-data access	EHDS, GDPR	L5
Adopt anonymisation and synthetic-data procedures	EHDS, GDPR	L5
Orient clinical data to HL7 FHIR and the OMOP CDM, with DCAT-AP for metadata	EHDS	L5

Continued on next page

Task / artefact	Affected regulation(s)	Layer
<i>Layer 6. Project management and audit</i>		
Maintain a central project registry	EU grant rules	L6
Keep pre-assembled audit packs covering timesheets, procurement and approvals	EU grant rules	L6
<i>Cross-cutting</i>		
Adopt a management-system roadmap toward ISO/IEC 27001, 27701 and 42001	cross-cutting	all

Note. The layer references follow the IAA in Section 7. The baseline is a transferable minimum rather than an exhaustive or certified compliance list. The scope and the obligatory status of each item depend on the risk class of the specific system under the AI Act and on the applicable national law.

10. The “Brussels Effect”

The central claim of this study is that the gap between regulation and trustworthy AI in health is institutional rather than legislative. Statutory text is necessary, but it does not by itself make an institution compliant. Compliance is created and maintained through local roles, reusable templates, documented decisions and structured workflows. This point matters directly for AI governance. AI systems are developed, tested and used by institutions, not by governments. The safety and trustworthiness of health AI are therefore determined where research teams handle patient data, classify system risk, secure infrastructure and record governance decisions. A state may adopt an exemplary AI law and still host unsafe AI if its institutions cannot operationalise that law. Conversely, an institution in a country without a dedicated AI law may still build trustworthy systems if it has a strong internal governance architecture. Institutional regulatory capacity is therefore not a secondary step after legislative transposition. It is the practical condition that determines whether regulation becomes safe AI in practice (Mantelero, 2018; Kaminski and Malgieri, 2021).

525 This institutional view also clarifies how the *Brussels Effect* operates in
practice (Bradford, 2020). Institutions in non-EU candidate countries often feel
the pull of European digital law before national transposition is complete. A
third-country faculty that cannot demonstrate alignment with the AI Act, NIS2
and the GDPR may struggle to join leading European funding instruments,
530 clinical partnerships and data-sharing networks. The Brussels Effect is the
external pressure that makes compliance difficult to avoid. The institution is
the internal site where compliance is either achieved or lost. Together, these
two points change how research excellence should be understood in Widening
contexts. Technical capacity remains essential, but it is not enough. Regulatory
535 capacity-building should be treated as part of research excellence rather than
as a separate administrative burden.

This situation also creates an opportunity. Several regimes, including NIS2
and the EHDS, are still operationally immature even within Member States.
This is consistent with documented differences in EHDS readiness across the
540 Union (Kessissoglou et al., 2024). Third-country institutions can use this period
to design clean multi-regime compliance layers from the beginning. If they do
so, they may avoid the more expensive task of retrofitting fragmented legacy
procedures later.

Several limitations qualify these claims. This is a single formative case, and
545 the implemented mechanisms have not yet been evaluated for long-term effec-
tiveness. Some constraints also sit outside the institution. These include the
limited capacity of the national supervisory authority and the transfer frictions
created by third-country status. No institutional architecture can fully remove
those constraints. Finally, the AI-Act supervisory mapping remains provisional.
550 It is an analogy rather than a formal designation until national legislation con-
firms the competent authorities.

11. Conclusion

The convergence of the European digital rulebook changes what AI-in-health research institutions must be able to do. They can no longer rely on separate administrative procedures for data protection, cybersecurity, AI governance and health-data access. They need an integrated institutional architecture that can manage these regimes together.

This study has shown why that shift matters. Through a three-phase readiness model and a benchmarking exercise between two research institutions, it identifies compliance as an operational challenge rather than only a legislative one. Laws set the requirements, but institutions give those requirements practical effect. This is especially important for AI in health, because AI systems are developed, tested and deployed by universities, research centres, hospitals and companies. The safety and trustworthiness of those systems are therefore determined inside the institution, through its roles, procedures, registers, technical controls and documentation practices.

For Widening and third-country institutions, this conclusion has direct implications. Regulatory capacity-building should not be treated as a distraction from research excellence. It is one of the conditions that allows institutions to participate credibly in European AI-in-health research. The six-layer Institutional Accountability Architecture proposed in this article offers a transferable framework for that purpose. It helps research-performing institutions connect innovation with accountable governance under the overlapping requirements of the GDPR, NIS2, the AI Act and the EHDS.

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Data availability. This study draws on internal institutional procedures, project documents and benchmarking notes that are not publicly available owing to their administrative and confidential nature.

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